

Numerical investigation of the combustion modes resulting from the auto-ignition of hot spots in hydrogen air mixtures

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Abstract

This present work had three main aims: 1.) to generate a detonation peninsula for hydrogen in air in a planar configuration, 2.) to analyze the specific interactions between the autoignition wave and acoustic wave within the detonation regime and 3.) to explore how the peninsula changes for rich hydrogen in air mixtures. It was found that compared to leaner mixtures, a rich mixture exhibits a narrower detonation peninsula. The reason for this deserves further investigation. It was also found that at similar ξ values within the detonation regime, the smaller the hotspot, the higher the local Mach number when the transition to detonation begins. This could offer an explanation as to why detonations occur more readily in smaller hotspots.

Introduction

In a combustible mixture of fuel and oxidizer, detonations can result from hot spot autoignition. In a constant volume combustor (CVC) or a shockless explosion combustor (SEC), a transition to detonation is similar to super-knock observed in piston engines and can have damaging effects on the system's mechanical structure. Bradley et al [1] concluded that detonations occur when the autoignition wave and the pressure wave reinforce each other in a sufficiently reactive mixture. Gu et al [2] identified different autoignition propagation modes including detonation, a subsonic reaction front and a supersonic reaction front. Bradley et al [1][2], using numerical simulations of syngas, created a detonation peninsula quantifying the bounds for each autoignition propagation regime using the dimensionless parameters ξ and ϵ .

The parameter ξ represents the ratio between the speed of sound (a) and the autoignition wave speed (u_a). Zeldovich et al [3] concluded that the hot-spot induced autoignition wave speed is inversely proportional to the ignition delay time (τ_{ig}). The parameter ϵ represents the number of excitation heat releases feeding into the pressure wave during the resident time in a hotspot with radius r_0 and therefore the amount of energy unloaded into the acoustic wave. The heat release is quantified by the excitation time (τ_e) defined as the time interval between 5% and the maximum heat release rate. The equations for the two parameters are as follows:

$$\xi = a/u_a = a/\left(\frac{dr}{dT} * \frac{dT}{d\tau_{ig}}\right), \quad \epsilon = (r_0/a)/(\tau_e) \quad (1)$$

where: $\frac{dT}{d\tau_{ig}}$ is given by:

$$\frac{dT}{d\tau_{ig}} = \lim_{\Delta T \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta \tau_{ig}} \right) \quad (2)$$

From equation 1 it is clear that the higher the radial temperature gradient ($\frac{dT}{dr}$), then the slower the autoignition wave speed u_a .

Whilst Bradley et al [4] found the detonation peninsula created with syngas to be applicable over a wide range of fuels, Pan et al [5] found that despite qualitative similarities, the detonation peninsula is quantitatively different between fuels due to differences in the physiochemical properties. These differences affect the processes of diffusion and transport. Gao et al [6] also found that for hydrogen hotspots in a spherical configuration, the detonation peninsula changes shape for different initial conditions including equivalence ratio. It was also noted that the hydrogen detonation peninsula exhibited a "rhino horn" shape due to large values of ϵ suppressing detonations and pushing the regime towards a subsonic reaction front. This phenomenon has only been observed for hydrogen because for other fuels, detonation development is usually easier for larger hotspots.

This present work aims to generate a detonation peninsula for hydrogen in air in a planar configuration. This paper will analyze the specific interactions between the autoignition wave and acoustic wave within the detonation regime to determine what affects the occurrence of a detonation. Lastly this paper aims to explore how the peninsula changes for a rich hydrogen in air mixture.

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Numerical models and methods used

In this present study, a one-dimensional model and planar geometry is assumed as shown in figure 1. There is a symmetrical boundary on the left wall and a reflective boundary on the right wall. The adiabatic domain is initially filled with a static hydrogen air mixture and the initial pressure (P_0) and equivalence ratio (Φ) are uniformly distributed across the domain. The domain length (r_w) is fixed at 5mm and the hot spot length (r_0) is to be specified. The domain outside of the hot spot has an initial temperature of T_0 with the hotspot at the center of the domain. The temperature distribution within the hot spot is shown in figure 1 and described by equation 3.

Figure 1

Model of hotspot initial conditions adopted in the present study.

$$T(t=0, r) = \begin{cases} T_0 + (r - r_0) \frac{dT}{dr} & \text{for } 0 \leq r \leq r_0 \\ T_0 & \text{for } r_0 \leq r \leq r_w \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The 1-D simulation of the transient auto-ignition reaction front is simulated using the INSFLA code provided by the Karlsruhe Institute of technology [7]. This code provides time and space solutions for 1-D reacting flows with multi-step chemistry and multi-species transport modes through solving the mass, energy momentum and species conservation equations. The code uses fully compressible Navier-Stokes equations, an implicit time integration method and performs spatial discretization using the finite difference method. For this study, a grid with an initial uniform grid size of $7\mu\text{m}$ is used. The INSFLA code works with lagrangian coordinates where the domain grid points are a function of the fluid element-based coordinates (ψ), and ψ remains constant between grid points. The grid points move when there is thermal expansion. Therefore, the propagating wave and detonation zones are covered by a finer mesh with a minimum mesh size of $1\mu\text{m}$.

The dimensionless parameters from equation 1 are evaluated for the temperature located at the center of the hotspot and are calculated using the Cantera package [8]. Gao et al [6] used the hydrogen mechanism developed by Keromnes et al [9]. However, Zukhov [10] found

that the Konnov mechanism [11] showed greater agreement with experimental data when compared to other hydrogen air mechanisms. The ignition delay times for a range of temperatures were simulated by both the INSFLA code and Cantera for both the Keromnes and Konnov hydrogen air mechanisms as well as mechanisms proposed by Connaire et al [12] and Burke et al [13].

Figure 2

Comparison of mechanisms for the simulation of ignition delay times for stoichiometric hydrogen in air at 40 atm

As shown in figure 2, there is good agreement between all mechanisms when evaluated for a stoichiometric hydrogen in air mixture at 40 atm. Therefore, for this present study the Keromnes mechanism was selected to improve comparability with [6].

In this present study, only the interaction of the autoignition wave with the acoustic wave will be analyzed. The effect of reflections on the wall will not be considered.

Results and discussion

3.1: Detonation peninsula for stoichiometric and rich hydrogen in air mixtures

For an initial domain temperature and pressure of 1000 K and 40 atm, the autoignition of several hotspots of different lengths and temperature gradients were simulated. The resulting regimes and resulting detonation peninsula are plotted in figure 3. This was done for both a stoichiometric hydrogen air mixture and a rich mixture with an equivalence ratio of $\Phi = 2$. The same criteria used in [6] was chosen to identify a detonation. This criterion was:

- 1.) the maximum pressure is at least 2 times the constant volume adiabatic equilibrium pressure (P_E)
- 2.) the reaction front propagations speed reaches at least 90% of the Chapman Jouguet (C-J) detonation speed

Figure 3

Detonation peninsula for hydrogen in air at 40 atm and 1000 K. The orange points are for the stoichiometric case where $\Phi = 1$ and the blue points are for the rich case where $\Phi = 2$. The lines encase the boundaries for developing detonations.

As observed in figure 3, the detonation peninsula for both equivalence ratios exhibit the “rhino horn” shape observed in [6]. The range of ξ values for which detonations develop increases as the hotspot length and corresponding ε value decreases. For the rich mixture, the detonation development regime is narrower meaning detonations are less likely to develop compared to leaner mixtures.

3.2: The mechanisms underlying detonation development

To better understand the mechanisms underlying detonation development, three different cases for a hotspot of 1 mm length at different ξ values in a stoichiometric mixture (highlighted in figure 3) are examined. The corresponding reaction front speeds and pressure profiles are shown in figure 4.

As seen in figure 4 case A, where there is a lower ξ value and thus a higher reaction front speed, the initial reaction front speed is near the Chapman-Jouguet Speed. The coupling of the reaction front with the acoustic wave can be seen in the pressure profile and the resulting detonation can be seen by the reaction wave settling at the Chapman-Jouguet speed. As case A is at the boundary of the supersonic reaction front, a lower ξ value would have led to an even higher initial reaction front speed and no coupling with the acoustic wave. In case B there is higher ξ value and therefore a lower reaction front speed. However, there is still coupling with the acoustic wave as can be seen in the pressure profile and a detonation occurs. In case C with an even larger ξ value and correspondingly lower initial reaction wave speed, the initial reaction wave speed is too low to couple with the acoustic wave enough to form a detonation.

Figure 4

Graphs of the reaction front propagation speed (u_a) and the pressure profiles at different time steps, against the domain position for a 1 mm hotspot in a stoichiometric hydrogen in air mixture at 1000 K and 40 atm for 3 cases:

- A temperature gradient of 150 K/m and ξ value of 5.82 close to the supersonic boundary. The time sequence is 1: 2559.25 μs , 2: 2559.69 μs , 3: 2560.06 μs , 4: 2560.44 μs , 5: 2560.92 μs .
- A temperature gradient of 1250 K/m and ξ value of 48.6 within the detonation regime. The time sequence is 1: 2536.2 μs , 2: 2536.4 μs , 3: 2536.74 μs , 4: 2537.17 μs .
- A temperature gradient of 1550 K/m and ξ value of 60.2 within the subsonic reaction wave regime. The time sequence is: 1: 2526.59 μs , 2: 2526.78 μs , 3: 2526.95 μs , 4: 2527.16 μs , 4: 2527.39 μs .

3.3 Detonation development with hot spot size

From the detonation peninsula in figure 3, it was observed that the detonation regimes became narrower as the hotspot length and correspondingly ϵ values increased. In [6] this behavior was found to be specific to hydrogen. To investigate this further, hotspots of different lengths at a temperature gradient of 1100 K/m and at 1000 K and 40 atm in a stoichiometric mixture were investigated. The corresponding ξ values for the hot spots are displayed in table 2. As seen in table 2, with the same temperature gradient, the hotspots of different sizes have comparable ξ values. A line showing the approximate positions of these hotspots on the peninsular is shown in figure 3.

Hotspot length (mm)	ξ
0.7	42.36
1.0	42.20
1.2	42.10
1.5	41.94
1.8	41.79
2.1	41.63
2.3	41.53
2.5	41.43
4.0	40.67

Table 1

Table of ξ values calculated for hotspots of different lengths at a temperature gradient of 1100 K/m in a stoichiometric hydrogen air mixture at 1000 K and 40 atm.

Figure 5A shows the reaction front speed relative to the origin for the hotspots of different lengths. The speed of sound and Chapman-Jouguet speed displayed are those calculated for the mixture conditions (1000 K and 40 atm). It appears that the smaller the hotspot, the earlier along the domain length that the transition to detonation occurs. However, the state of the gas just ahead of the reaction wave will affect the relative speed of the reaction front as well as the local speed of sound. The speed of sound and the bulk fluid velocity 0.1 mm ahead of the reaction front at each timestep was calculated and plotted in figure 5B and 5C.

From figure 5B it can be seen that the local speed of sound is much higher than that of the mixture. This is due to the increased temperature of the fresh gas ahead of the reaction front. Moreover, as seen in figure 5C, the bulk fluid velocity especially during the transition to detonation, is significant which will greatly affect the reaction front velocity relative to the unburned mixture. The local Mach number (M) of the reaction front was calculated using the local speed of sound (a_l) and local bulk fluid velocity (u_l) as follows:

$$M = (u_a - u_l)/a_l \quad (4)$$

and plotted in figure 5D. The transition point is considered as the domain position when the Mach number starts to rise rapidly. As seen in figure 5D, the smaller the hotspot, the higher the local Mach number at a given domain position. As the Mach numbers for all the hotspots at the transition point are below one, a higher Mach number means the closer the reaction front speed is to the speed of sound. This explains the stronger pairing and therefore the steeper acceleration to detonation along the domain length for the smaller hotspots.

A possible explanation as to why detonations appear to occur more readily in smaller hotspots is as follows: The smaller the hotspot, the higher the Mach number when transition occurs. There is likely a minimum Mach number required for the coupling effect with the acoustic wave to result in a detonation. For larger hotspots, the Mach number at the domain transition point will be lower, resulting in a weaker detonation. In some cases the Mach number may even be insufficient to result in a detonation. Further work needs to be done to explain the reason for this higher Mach number in smaller hot spots.

Conclusions

The coupling of the auto-ignition wave with the acoustic wave for a given hotspot determines if a detonation occurs. The hydrogen detonation peninsula exhibits a ‘‘rhino horn’’ shape when tested in a planar geometry. It was found that rich mixtures have a narrower detonation peninsula when compared to leaner mixtures. Further works needs to be done to find the reason for this. It was also found that detonations developed more easily in smaller hotspots. The bulk fluid velocity and the changes in the local speed of sound were found to be significant at the conditions explored. When computing the local Mach number, it was found that for a given temperature gradient, the smaller the hotspot, the higher the Mach number at the position where transition began. The Mach number at the transition position for larger hotspots will be lower which could result in a weaker pairing with the acoustic wave. Assuming there is a minimum Mach number at which a transition to detonation occurs, in some cases the Mach number may be insufficient to result in a detonation. This is a possible explanation as to why detonations are seen to develop more readily in smaller hotspots. The reason for the higher Mach number at transition for smaller hotspots deserves further investigation.

Figure 5

Reaction front properties against domain position for hotspots of different lengths at a temperature gradient of 1100 K/m, in a stoichiometric hydrogen air mixture at 1000 K and 40 atm.

5A – Reaction wave speed against domain position

5B – Speed of sound ahead of the reaction front against domain position

5C – Bulk fluid velocity ahead of the reaction front against the domain position

5D – Reaction front Mach number against domain position

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